

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE COMPETENCIES BASED ON INDIVIDUAL APPROACH IN EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *Coordination of pedagogical education directions, perspective planning, lack of communication and integration between educational stages, dispersion in the activities of educational subjects are the basis for creating pedagogical education clusters. The article describes the need for personnel, the issues of developing students' creative competencies based on an individual approach in the conditions of the educational cluster created in order to improve the quality of education.*

Keywords: *education, integration, entity, quality, cluster, skill, quality, experience, action.*

A cluster is an association of various companies, enterprises, suppliers of specialized services, resources and infrastructure, scientific and educational organizations connected by regional proximity, complementary and individual enterprises, increasing the competitive advantages of companies. The cooperation of all its members is carried out continuously through the exchange of personnel, technologies, innovations, sharing of resources, services, infrastructure development and marketing [1].

In a cluster, two main tasks are performed at the same time, such as cost reduction due to the proximity of similar firms and the diffusion of innovations from one firm to another, which ensures a continuous increase in productivity in the cluster as a whole [2].

Recognition of the importance of stimulating the development of innovation within science, education and production led to the establishment of National Systems of Innovation in a number of European countries in the 1990s. Various integrated complexes began to receive special support from innovative firms, technology parks, and others. The concept of national innovative systems, as well as the establishment of cooperation between science, education and business as the main institutions of the modern economy, can lead to fundamental research and the production of various products or services.

Connecting clusters with the field of education, G. I. Muhamedov gives a broader definition of this concept in the article "Innovative cluster of pedagogical education: need, necessity, result" [3]. In it, a new system related to the creation of an innovative cluster of pedagogical education due to the study of existing shortcomings in the education system and their analysis, coordination of pedagogical education directions, perspective planning, slowness of communication and integration between educational stages, disparity in the activities of educational subjects, unsatisfaction of the need for pedagogic personnel in the region, and a decrease in the quality of education it is noted that it was created.

The following variants of cluster formation are highlighted in the literature: "from the bottom up" - a cluster is created as a result of the integration of separate projects and programs, in which the future participants of the cluster are the initiators; "from top to bottom" - regional authorities determine the strategy of forming a cluster, allocating funds and creating a coordinating council; mixed - combines the first and second options. In many developed countries, there is a tendency to use the first and second approaches to identify (discover) innovative areas and provide conditions for further development [4].

Currently, the formation of clusters is carried out in many countries of the world. The cluster approach is actively used in various sectors of the economy and in the practice of higher education. Analysis of world experience provides the following options for creating clusters: 1) clusters resulting from cooperation between enterprises; 2) clusters based on innovative structure (creating organizational forms of innovative activity with the need for close cooperation of industrial production with the academic and higher education sector, formation of high-tech and knowledge-intensive production, technological and scientific-technical innovations, business incubator or technology park production dependent); 3) clusters around research or technological universities. It should be noted that each of the presented options requires the participation of higher education institutions [1].

The analysis of the philosophical, psychological, pedagogical and methodical literature on the problem of developing students' creative competences based on an individual approach in the conditions of the educational cluster shows that the issues of personality development have always been a concern of humanity. During the Renaissance [6], the Enlightenment [5] and later periods of civilization development, great importance was attached to the individual and his improvement, and various ideas were put forward to realize this goal.

Most scientists studying the problem of individual approach emphasize the need to take into account the individual psychological characteristics of students in this process. Modern pedagogy has come closer to psychology by accepting the orientation of the individual, recognizing the right of a person to realize his own needs and his own life path. This is evidenced by the prevalence of "person", "subject", "individuality", "value", "meaning", "development", "support" and other terms in pedagogical works, the interpretation of which is involved in the works of psychologists [7].

The individual approach assumes that the student's nationality, gender, age, individual-psychological characteristics, and status are taken into account as much as possible in the process of teaching any academic subject. This attention is carried out through their educational tasks, the character of communication with the student, the content and the form itself. The questions, comments, and assignments given to the student, in the conditions of this approach, stimulate their personal, intellectual activity, support and guide their educational activities without excessively correcting mistakes, blunders, unsuccessful actions. Thus, not only the individual psychological characteristics of students, but also the formation and further development of the student's psyche, his cognitive processes, personal qualities, activity characteristics, etc. are taken into account.

The individual approach is considered as an approach aimed at creating favorable opportunities for the learner, the main goal of education is to ensure the harmonious development of the learner in all aspects. In the individual approach, the student's personality is placed in the center of the educational process, and all components of the educational process are directed to his education and upbringing. Since the primary goal of the educational process is to provide

education, directing all opportunities and tools to increase the personal and professional capabilities of the student, to bring his knowledge, skills and abilities to the level of competence, serves to increase the quality and efficiency of education.

The development of students' creative competences based on an individual approach in the conditions of the educational cluster is related to the development of literary and creative abilities and their own creative abilities and self-development on a professional basis.

R. Epstein was the first to put the concept of "creative competence" into scientific use, and he describes this phenomenon as adaptive application of acquired knowledge, readiness to independently fill the knowledge system, and striving for self-improvement [7]. Creativity in pedagogy is creativity, the ability to accept and create new, non-standard thinking, to create many original and useful ideas.

Student's creative competence, according to N.A. Timofeeva's interpretation, is an integral multifactorial quality of a person, which determines the development of students' creative abilities on a professional basis. It is independent personal learning in a complex dialectical relationship with professional competence, which shows the possibility of coincidence and separation [8].

The development of students' creative competences based on an individual approach in the conditions of an educational cluster is a multifactorial quality of a person, a system of intellectual, emotional, moral, willful, etc. knowledge, skills, personal qualities and experience that determines the development of a person's creative abilities and allows for the creation of many unique characteristics. level of non-standard and useful ideas and products, as well as their flexibility, determine the theoretical and practical readiness of a person to act creatively in various life and professional situations.

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